

Study Task

Consider the various types of assessments in CS 1101. As you know, the final grade is based on work on the following assessments:

- TopHat questions.
- zyBooks activities, which in this problem we consider the two types of activities defined in zyBooks, which are participation and challenge activities.
- Programming assignments.
- Exams, that are administered during the semester.
- Final exam.

A description of each of these assessments will be given. Based on the descriptions, your task is two-fold:

1. Create a UML class diagram that defines the members (i.e., fields and methods) of each class. In addition, the class diagram should also be a class hierarchy that defines the inheritance relationships of the classes.
2. Implement each class as a Java file with skeleton code in the classes.

In Programming Assignment 11, we provided you with a detailed description of each class, which included a class diagram that contained the fields and methods for each class. In this assignment, we will describe the fields and methods that a class should be associated with, but as you know – through inheritance – declarations of some fields and implementation of some methods can in fact be placed in another class (i.e., a super class). This is because there are several techniques/terms related to Object-Oriented Programming that, if applied, can increase the quality of the code. Applying these techniques and placing fields and methods in certain classes will help make the classes **better organized** and **reduce code duplication** as much as possible. It is your task to determine where each field and method should be placed to increase the quality of the code.

Task 1 – Create a UML class diagram

You are to create a UML class diagram based on your determination of where each field and method should be placed. Draw a class diagram for each class that will be described. You can use the class diagram format given in Programming Assignment 11 as an example. The following is the class diagram for House class.

Note that the class diagram includes the following information:

- The name of the class.
- Whether the class extends another class. *Note: you do not need to include this part, because the inheritance relationship should be identified using arrows.*
- Overloaded constructors. *Note: you do not need to include constructor descriptions.*
- Fields, including their type.
- Methods, including their parameters and return types (if any).

In terms of specifying that a class extends or inherits another class, you can use a line that connects the two classes with an arrow pointing to the base/parent/super class. The lecture slides should have examples of such inheritance relationships that are specified in a UML diagram.

If you determine that other classes are needed in the class hierarchy, feel free to add them. Again, the goal is to make the class hierarchy as organized as possible with as little duplication as possible.

The UML diagram with class specifications and inheritance relationships can be drawn by hand or developed in a program like Word or Powerpoint. In both cases, submit a PDF file. For drawings, scan the drawing and save the scan as a PDF file. Included with this assignment is a Powerpoint file called **uml-diagram.pptx**. This file includes the UML diagram for the PA11-B (i.e., the class diagrams and inheritance relationships). You are welcome to update the UML diagram for this assignment and then submit a PDF version of the Powerpoint file.

Task 2 - Implement each class with skeleton code

You are to create Java class files for each class that will be described. Add fields to each class based on your determination of where each field should be placed. Also, create methods in the classes where they should be implemented. You do not need to implement method, but rather you can simply define the method header (i.e., the return type of the method, if it returns something, the name of the method, and the parameters of the method, if it has any). If a method returns something, then return a default-type value for that type (e.g., if the method returns a string, then return an empty string).

The following pages are the descriptions of the classes with information on the fields and methods that are associated with each class. Again, it may be the case some fields and methods should actually be placed in another class to take advantage of inheritance, with the least of amount of duplication of code and provide for better organization of the code. Note that for fields, the name of the field is followed by its type (and separated by a colon). For methods, the name of the method is followed by parentheses. Parameters and their types are listed inside the parentheses, where each parameter name and its type separated by a colon. If a method returns a value, then the return type included after a colon.

=== TopHat question ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the TopHat question.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the question. All TopHat questions are worth 1 point.

- **topic : String**

The topic associated with the TopHat question.

- **participationCount : int**

The number of students who participated in the TopHat question.

=== TopHat question ===

Methods:

- **getPercentage(score : double) : double**

This method returns the percentage of the score based on the full points of the TopHat question. For example, since each TopHat question is worth 1 point, if getPercentage was passed 1.0, then the method should return $1.0 / 1$, which is 1.0.

- **getPercentage(totalEnrollment: int) : double**

This method returns the percentage of students who participated in the TopHat question based on the total enrollment that is passed as the parameter. For example, if 200 students participated in the TopHat question, if getPercentage is passed 250, then the method should return $200 / 250$, which is 0.8.

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of a TopHat question. For example, if the name of the TopHat question is "Inheritance", the full score 1 point, the topic is "Methods that can be called by an object", and the participation count is 200, then the following string should be returned.

```
Name: Inheritance
Full score: 1
Topic of question: Methods that can be called by an object
Number of students who participated: 200
```

=== Participation activity ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the participation activity.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the participation activity.

- **chapter : int**

The chapter in zyBooks that the participation activity is associated with.

- **numberOfProblems : int**

The number of problems in the participation activity.

- **hasTrueFalse : boolean**

Whether the participation activity has at least one true/false question.

- **hasMultipleChoice : boolean**

Whether the participation activity has at least one multiple choice question.

- **hasAnimation : boolean**

Whether the participation activity has at least one animation.

=== Participation activity ===

Methods:

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of a participation activity. For example, if the name of the participation activity is "ZY-PA-8A", the full score 38 points, the chapter is 8, the number of problems is 15, there are multiple choice questions, but no true/false questions and animations, then the following string should be returned.

```
Name: ZY-PA-8A
Full score: 38
Chapter: 8
Number of problems: 15
- No true or false question(s)
- Has multiple choice question(s)
- No animation
```

=== Challenge activity ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the challenge activity.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the challenge activity.

- **chapter : int**

The chapter in zyBooks that the challenge activity is associated with.

- **numberOfProblems : int**

The number of problems in the challenge activity.

- **hasCoding: boolean**

Whether the challenge activity has at least one coding problem.

- **hasStepThrough : boolean**

Whether the challenge activity has at least one multiple choice questions.

=== Challenge activity ===

Methods:

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of a challenge activity. For example, if the name of the challenge activity is "ZY-CA-8A", the full score 11 points, the chapter is 8, the number of problems is 6, there are coding problems, but no step through problems, then the following string should be returned.

```
Name: ZY-CA-8A
Full score: 11
Chapter: 8
Number of problems: 6
- Has coding problem(s)
- No code step-through problem(s)
```

=== Programming assignment ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the programming assignment.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the programming assignment.

- **numberOfProblems : int**

The number of problems for the programming assignment.

- **hasWarmup : boolean**

Whether the programming assignment has at least one warmup problem.

=== Programming assignment ===

Methods:

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of a programming assignment. For example, if the name of the programming assignment is "PA-02", the full score 40 points, the number of problems is 4, and there are coding problems, then the following string should be returned.

```
Name: PA-02
Full score: 40
Number of problems: 4
- Has warmup problem(s)
```

=== Exam ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the exam.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the exam.

- **numberOfProblems : int**

The number of problems for the exam.

=== Exam ===

Methods:

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of an exam. For example, if the name of the exam is "Exam 1", the full score 100 points, and the number of problems is 8, then the following string should be returned.

```
Name: Exam 1
Full score: 100
Number of problems: 8
```

=== Final exam ===

Fields:

- **name : String**

The name of the final exam.

- **fullScore : int**

The full points for the final exam.

- **numberOfProblems : int**

The number of problems for the final exam.

- **preExam1Topics : int**

The percentage (a value between 0–100 inclusive) of pre-Exam 1 topics included in the final exam.

- **preExam2Topics : int**

The percentage (a value between 0–100 inclusive) of pre-Exam 2 topics included in the final exam.

- **preFinalExamTopics : int**

The percentage (a value between 0–100 inclusive) of pre-Final Exam topics included in the final exam.

=== Final exam ===

Methods:

- **toString : String**

Returns the *string representation* of a final exam. For example, if the name of the final exam is "The Big One", the full score 100 points, the number of problems is 1000, the percentage of pre-Exam 1 topics is 10, the percentage of pre-Exam 2 topics is 30, and the percentage of pre-Final Exam topics is 60, then the following string should be returned. **Note: the percentages above are not reflective of the real final exam on April 28.**

```
Name: The Big One  
Full score: 100  
Number of problems: 1000  
Topics before Exam 1: 10%  
Topics before Exam 2: 30%  
Topics before Final Exam: 60%
```

Now if you have finished this study task, please return to the Instruction file to finish the rest of the steps.

